

Assessing Flow Pattern of Sabarmati River Portion at Hirpura Barrage Site Gujarat, India using HEC-RAS Hydrodynamic Models and Physical Models for Gate Operation

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Abstract

A barrage is proposed to be constructed across river Sabarmati 60 km downstream of Daroi dam to create reservoir within the bank for recharging and water demand of nearby areas. For analyzing the flow pattern and assessing the hydraulic parameters of Hipura barrage on Sabarmati river near Hirpura village of Mehsana District of Gujarat, a 3D physical model with geometrically similar scale 1:80 for river reach 3km (1km upstream and 2km downstream) and for assessing the adequate energy dissipating arrangement a sectional model with scale 1:40 are used. These experimental observations on physical models are carried out at GERI (Gujarat Engineering Research Institute), have been used to calibrate HEC RAS based model for Manning's roughness (n). The calibrated parameters of model are used to compute the hydraulic parameters in HEC RAS model in the steady state condition of flow in the river reach for 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% of design discharge 16785 m³/s (5.9 lakh cusec). From the observed values of velocities on the left bank the protection work about 500m is required on upstream side as well as downstream side. Present paper describes the flow, analysis using 30 cross sections and topographical details of river reach under study in existing conditions of river without the barrage and with barrage in position. The results of the prediction run indicated that the FRL 99.00m can be maintained by opening 19 vertical lift gates up to 25 % discharge. The discharge exceeds 25% flood all gates should be kept open in free flow condition.

Keywords: Physical model, steady flow, discharge, river reach, barrage, calibration.

List of symbols: Water depth(m), R.L (m), Velocity(m/s) , Discharge (m³/s), upstream (u/s), downstream (d/s)

1 INTRODUCTION

Sabarmati river is one of the prominent west flowing rivers of Gujarat. It originates from Aravalli rang of Udaipur District of Rajasthan and meets the gulf of Khambhat of Arabian sea after travelling 371 km. Dharoi dam is only major dam constructed at 80 km upper reach in the main river in 1978 for irrigation, power generation and flood control considering maximum discharge 21662 m³/s (7.64 Lakh cusec). ("Sabarmati river basin Govt. of India, Ministry of Water Resources 2014, project volume") Most of the seasons except monsoon this river remains dry and there is no free flow of water in the downstream reach of Dharoi dam (Kumar et.al 1999). Other medium existing hydraulic structures on this river are Lakroda barrage 112km, Sant Sarover barrage 169km and Vasna Barrage 201km from Dharoi dam. The downstream reach beyond 30km from the Dharoi dam, close to the river bank such as Vijapur, Hirpura and other villages of Mehsana district remain water scarce. To meet the water demand and recharging the surrounding 60 km d/s of Dharoi Dam, a barrage near Hirpura Village is proposed to be constructed. (Water Resource dept. Govt of Gujarat, 2017)

Physical models are the best tools for solving the complex flow problems, used worldwide to evaluate the flow parameters and the performance of the structure, based on that changes in the design can be possible (Rajaratnametal.,1990).The Central Design Organization (CDO) has designed the barrage structure for maximum discharge 16785 m³/s (5.9 lakh cusec). The studies are carried out at G.E.R.I. on 3D comprehensive

(scale 1:80) and sectional model Scale 1:40).

Major Hydraulic Structures on Sabarmati river

Figure 1 Major hydraulic structures on river Sabarmati from its originating place to merging at sea

HEC-RAS software version 5.0.3 is used in the present study. This software provides the facility to carry out 1D steady flow analysis, un-steady flow analysis, and sediment transport study/mobile bed computation in the river Channel. The celebration of Manning's (n) in HEC-RAS model for the river reach of Sabarmati is done at low discharges and validation at higher discharges for water levels observed on physical model as well as theoretically obtained from CDO. Prediction runs were taken in HEC-RAS for all range of discharges for water levels and velocities. The HEC-RAS 1D is run without and with the barrage structure. Fig 1 indicates the major hydraulic structures on river Sabarmati from its originating place to merging at sea. Fig 2 shows the meander portion and the location of proposed barrage.

Figure 2 Image showing the portion of Sabarmati river and location of barrage

2 DATA FORSTUDY

To assess the hydraulic parameters of barrage, topographical data close to the barrage location are essential. The study reach of the river Sabarmati is about 3km (1 km u/s and 2 km d/s from the barrage location). Topographical map (CAD Map) showing contours, levels, bank lines, bank area and locations of existing structures was provided by G.E.R.I. (Gujarat Engineering Research Institute). The Barrage is designed for 5.9 lacs cusecs flood ($16,785 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$) the maximum flood. Maximum observed flood in Sabarmati river was 3.1 lack cusecs ($8778 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$) in the year 2006. In order to perform the 1D steady flow hydrodynamic modelling the input data include : (1) River stations (2) Elevation coordinates (3) Left and right bank station location (4) Reach lengths [left flood way , stream centerline and right flood way of adjacent cross sections] (5) Manning's roughness coefficient (6) Slope of the reach (1:1200). The details of structure are given in table 1.

Table 1 Structural details of barrage (Source : C.D.O Gandhinagar, GERI,)

Sr. no.	Components	Details
1	Discharge	5.9 lacs cusec ($16785 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$)
2	Type of structure	Barrage
3	Length of structure	396.5m
4	High Flood Level (HFL)	RL 105.81m
5	Full Reservoir level (FRL)	RL 99.00m
6	Deepest bed level	RL 91.00m
7	Average river bed level	RL 92.34m
8	Number of gates (spans)	19 (18.5m each)
9	Gate size	18.5m X 4m
10	Pier thickness	2.5m
11	Crest RL	95.34m
12	Downstream apron floor length	40m
13	Upstream floor length	7m
14	Upstream cut off depth	5m
15	Downstream cut off depth	10m

3. METHODOLOGY

The study has been proceeded with the work on physical model as well 1D HEC-RAS and 2D HEC-RAS

3.1 Work on 3D Physical Model

The physical model was run for 10%, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% of design discharges. The flow pattern, water levels and velocities were observed in the close proximity of the structure. The flow was almost normal to the barrage axis for all range of discharges. From these observations the orientation of barrage seemed to be adequate. Table 2 below gives the water levels at selected four locations and Fig 3 shows the flow pattern during model run. These values were used to calibrate and validate the HEC-RAS model.

Table 2.Percentage discharge verses water levels at different locations in the river reach

%Discharge	W.L in m at ch 120m (physical model)	W.L in m at ch 550 m (physical model)	W.L in m at ch 850 m (physical model)	W.L in m at ch 2500 m (physical model)
10%	97.02	96.42	96.1	95.1
25%	99.43	98.92	98.37	97.26
50%	102.13	101.22	101.05	99.68
75%	104.32	103.22	103.02	101.69
100%	106.11	1104.92	104.71	103.33

Fig 3. 3D physical model run at 25% flood

3.2. Calibration and validation of HEC-RAS model

The HEC-RAS model was run for 10%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% floods with n values 0.028 and 0.03 to obtain the water levels at different locations in the river channel. The water levels computed in HEC-RAS were in a difference of 0.7 m and 0.6 m respectively with the water levels observed on the physical model at respective locations for different discharges. To obtain the closer values of water levels in HEC-RAS model with the observed water levels on physical model the n value 0.035 adopted for HEC-RAS is reasonable and with good agreement of water levels at different locations. The HEC-RAS model is calibrated with n values 0.035 for 10 % and 25 % low discharges, with this the water levels obtained in HEC-RAS model are closer to the water levels observed on the physical model with nominal difference of 0.3 m to 0.4 m. With this existing condition of river, running the model for higher discharges (75 % and 100 %) the water levels are further close to the observed levels on the physical model with nominal difference of 0.2 m to 0.3 m in the river channel. These values validate the HEC-RAS model for higher discharges. (Timbadiya, P.V. Patel, P.L., & Pore P.D. (2011)).

Fig 4. Comparison of water levels observed in physical model and obtained in HEC-RAS at 50 % flood

Fig 5. Comparison of water levels observed in physical model and obtained in HEC-RAS at 100 % flood

3.3 HEC-RAS 1D without the structure

The HEC-RAS 1D Model was run for 25 %, 50 %, 75 %, and 100 % discharge in steady flow condition. The cross-sections were added as the geometric data and the steady flow data included the discharge as the u/s boundary condition and normal depth as the d/s boundary condition. The model was run to obtain the results of the various water levels and velocities for each discharge in steady flow condition. Fig. 6 shows the representation of all the 30 c/s on the geometric data input.

Fig 6. Representation of all the 30 c/s on the geometric data window

3.4 HEC-RAS 1D with the structure

The HEC-RAS 1D model was run with the inline structure in place. The inline structure is between cross section 22 and 23. The fig 7 shows the barrage in position with arrangements of gates in HEC-RAS. The model is run keeping the similar condition of flow as in the case of without the structure to obtain the velocities and water levels.

Fig.7 The barrage between c/s 22 and c/s 23 in HEC- RAS model

3.5 Work on 2D Sectional physical model

The studies for performance of energy dissipaters, gate operation, scour is carried out on the sectional model with geometrically similar scale 1:40 on a 1.05m wide flume of length 25m. Two spans are reproduced on the sectional model. The two spans with the vertical lift gates, crest, upstream and downstream glacis, upstream and downstream apron, end sill, concrete blocks for protection of lifting of sand on the downstream side are reproduced on the model. The model discharge was released to the flume by the calibrated standing wave flume. Constant discharges of 10%, 15%, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% discharges were released to the model and for each discharge run the observations of hydraulic parameters were observed.

3.4 HEC-RAS 2D For Flood Spread

The topographical survey details up to 3km reach are available which are used for physical model and also in HEC-RAS 1D model. The flow analysis for further reach 3km upstream side and 9km in the downstream side is carried out with HEC-RAS 2D using SRTM DEM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission, Digital Elevation model) image. Loading the terrain and exporting image on the Ras mapper also defining the storage area and applying the 2D flow area mesh (Adding hydrograph and normal depth) the computation of hydraulic parameters is carried out.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Flow analysis without the structure (HEC-RAS1D)

In the existing condition of river without the barrage structure the water level on the upstream side of the location of the barrage observed on the physical model is RL 104.92m and with HEC-RAS it is RL 104.63m at the maximum design discharge. At 25% discharge the water level on the upstream side of barrage on physical and HEC-RAS model are RL 98.92m and RL 98.27m respectively. This discharge is bank full discharge in the river reach.

At 50 % flood, the velocity varies 4.16 m/s to 4.73m/s up to 300m on the upstream side of the structure near the banks on the physical model. The velocities on HEC-RAS model varies 3.8m/s to 4.42m/s at this discharge. At 100% discharge the maximum velocity observed on HEC-RAS model is 5.2m/s on upstream side of the location of the structure. This is due to steep higher left bank. These higher values of velocities can cause erosion on the left bank. Suitable protection works are required to be provided about 500m length on the up streamside.

4.2 Flow analysis with the structure (HEC-RAS1D)

Water level raised due to components of barrages like weir portion up to crest level and piers, the structure in position and keeping all gates open by 0.28m at low discharges whereas at higher discharges this afflux is 0.6m. The components of barrage are not giving much impact on rise of water level on the upstream side. The provision of crest RL 95.34m is adequate. The velocity computation with the structure in position in free flow condition of gate was almost same as in the previous case with marginal difference. Following table 3 the rise of water levels due to barrage inposition.

Table 3. Rise in water level 200m u/s side of barrage on cross section no. 26

% discharge	10%	25%	50%	75%	100%
With barrage	96.75	99.23	101.41	103.36	105.34
Without barrage	96.47	99.01	101.22	103.10	104.88
Rise in water level	0.28m	0.22m	0.19m	0.26m	0.46m

4.3 Gate openings with HEC-RAS 1D

The HEC-RAS 1D is run for gate operation. Keeping the u/s reservoir level at FRL(Full Reservoir level) 99.00m, the gate opening at various floods were computed in steady flow condition. The gate opening required 0.6m, 1.25m, 1.90m, 2.65m and 3.66m for 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% discharge respectively for maintaining FRL (Full Reservoir level)99.00m on the u/s side. When the discharge exceeded 25%, the upstream water level was higher than the FRL and above the gate opening. This was not the desired condition of gate operation. The gates can be operated up to 25% discharge for higher discharges, all 19 gates should be kept open in free flow condition of gate above the HFL(High flood level) 105.81m.

4.4 Flow analysis for water spreads and bank spillover with HEC-RAS2D

To assess the water spread at the maximum design floods in the extended portion of river 3km on the upstream side and 9km on the downstream side, the HEC -RAS 2D is run using DEM obtained from SRTM DEM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission, Digital Elevation model)of 30 m X 30 m resolution. At the maximum flood the no significant water spread is seen all along ther each except some locations of low bank levels and back flow in Nallas and Kotar which are much away from the barrage. Therefore, this location for barrage is appropriate. Following spread Fig. 8 shows the water spread at maximum discharge and velocity distribution all along the river channel. Details of flood spreads, water levels and velocities all along the extended reach are given in table 4.

Fig 8 water spread along the bank at the maximum discharge

Table 4 :Details of flood spreads, water levels and velocities all along the extended reach

Location	Water level(RL) (m)	Velocity (m/s)	Details of spreads
3km u/s	107.17	4.5	Back flow in small kotar (Nalla) about 500m on the left bank
2km u/s	106.52	4.25	Spreads of 100m width on right bank about 200m length on the left bank side
1km u/s	105.87	4.78	No significant spread
400m u/s	105.36	4.82	spreads about 40m on right bank side
200m u/s	105.17	4.45	Spread on right bank about 100m
1km d/s	103.26	5.68	No significant spread
2km d/s	103.09	5.43	No significant spread
3km d/s	102.13	5.20	No significant spread
4km d/s	101.70	3.99	Spread of about 200m on the left bank in the low-lying pocket
5km d/s	100.90	5.15	Spread of about 100m on the left bank in the low-lying pocket
6km d/s	99.11	4.38	No significant spread
7km d/s	98.56	5.15	No significant spread
8km d/s	97.67	4.12	No significant spread
9km d/s	97.21	4.36	No significant spread

4.5 Performance of energy dissipater on (2D) Sectional physical model

2D sectional physical model was run for various discharges ranging from 10% to 100% maintaining tail water level as observed on 3D comprehensive physical model for performance of energy dissipating arrangements. The hydraulic jump was formed at the toe of glacis up to 20% discharge. At 25% discharge weak jump was formed and at higher discharges the jump disappeared due to submerged condition of flow. The turbulence was within the length of apron therefore the provision of length of apron was adequate. Without river bed protection works the scour depth was 5.98m in the downstream side of apron against the provision of cut off depth 10m, therefore provision of cutoff depth is also adequate as per scour consideration.

6.0 CONCLUSION

1. The HEC-RAS model is calibrated with n values 0.035. The water levels obtained from HEC- RAS are in a good agreement with observed water levels on physical model. Single value of Manning's roughness(n) is enough for analysis purpose short length of river reach.
2. At 25% discharge the flow was within the defined banks, spillover was not observed, therefore this discharge is the bank full discharge. As the discharge exceeded 25 % flood, bank spillover started on the right bank area close to the barrage.
3. The hydraulic performance of barrage is satisfactory at the proposed location. The barrage is not giving much impact on rise of water levels. At the design flood the rise of water level without and with the barrage is 0.47m.
4. At 100% design discharge the flood levels are higher than the ground levels close to the barrage on right bank side for a width about 60m there after rising trend of ground levels exists which confines the flood. This would need extension of approach embankment about 60m beyond the left abutment towards the right bank matching with the higher ground levels.
5. At 100% discharge the maximum velocity observed on HEC-RAS model is 5.2m/s on upstream side of the location of the structure and 4.5m/s on the downstream side. These higher values of velocities can cause erosion on the left bank. Suitable protection works are required to be provided about 400m length on the upstream side.
6. The hydraulic jump was formed at the toe of glacis up to 20% discharge. At 25% discharge weak jump was formed and at higher discharges the jump disappeared due to submerged condition of flow. The turbulence was within the length of apron therefore the provision of length of apron was adequate.
7. The computed gate opening required 0.6m, 1.25m, 1.90m, 2.65m and 3.66m for 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% discharge respectively for maintaining FRL 99.00m on the u/s side. The gates can be operated up to 25% discharge for higher discharges, all 19 gates should be kept open in free flow condition of gate above the HFL 105.81m.
8. Significant flood spreads are not observed up to 9km d/s side and up to 3km u/s side, except at some locations of low bank levels and back flow in Nallas and Kotars which are far away from the barrage.

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